

17.02.2022

Newsletter

 COREnect

Public consultation

This public consultation aims to collect feedback on the intermediate roadmap. This feedback will be taken into consideration for the final roadmap.

[D3.4 Intermediate COREnect Industry Roadmap](#)

Have a look at the presentations:

- [Summary of Intermediate roadmap](#)
- [EG1 Compute and Store](#)
- [EG2 Connect and communicate](#)
- [EG3 Sense and Power](#)

The COREnect [White Paper](#) might be an interesting read as well.

We look forward to hearing your feedbacks for building the final COREnect roadmap!

“Microelectronics and connectivity: Europe going forward”: 3rd COREnect workshop

The main purpose of this workshop was to enhance the visibility of the European digital industry and to discuss about European connectivity and microelectronics matters.

[READ](#)

An Interview with Alexandros Kaloxylos

The 6G-IA is the voice of European Industry and Research for next generation networks and services. Its primary objective is to contribute to Europe's leadership on 5G, 5G evolution and SNS/6G research. The impact of microelectronics in the ICT sector is of prime concern for the members of the 6G-IA.

[READ](#)

COREnect is planning a Policy workshop!

Stay tuned to the COREnect website and social media channels for more details in the upcoming months!

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